

CONTROL OF THE FRACTURE OF ALUMINIUM-BASED MMCs BY THE HEAT TREATMENT OF C-FIBRE REINFORCEMENTS

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the results from a study on the effect of desize and post-desize heat treatments on epoxy-sized PAN-based carbon fibres. A SEM examination of unheat-treated and heat treated fibres is presented, as well as thermogravimetric measurements. This data is used to characterise the effect of heat treatment on the surface structure of these fibres and its subsequent effect on their static strengths.

Keywords: metal matrix composites, carbon, aluminium, fracture, heat treatment

1. INTRODUCTION

An examination of the load\displacement curves of continuous fibre reinforced MMCs shows that there are two distinct areas under these curves which relate to fracture energy, Figure 1. The first is associated with the initiation of fracture where the load increases from zero to a maximum, and the second with the propagation of the fracture. The latter shows the amount of resistance to failure and can dominate the toughness response of the material. To improve the fracture energy of a material both components of the fracture energy should therefore be considered. The preliminary results of such an investigation were presented previously [1] for a model unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced aluminium composite. This investigation showed that the normal fibre processing route (similar to that reported by Kim and Lee [2]), produced a material with a brittle response ie. low toughness. The introduction of an extra heat treatment into the processing route however, altered the fracture energy of the resulting composite by changing the failure response to one showing stable crack propagation (SCP). The load\displacement curves of these materials revealed that this extra heat treatment produced an enhanced propagation component to the fracture energy due to a reduction in the shear strength of the fibre\matrix interface. This resulted in fibre pull-out and debonding [1].

However, the initiation component of the fracture energy was not affected by such changes in failure mode and the failure strengths of the materials were similar irrespective of whether they showed brittle or SCP response. In all the materials the initiation component was very small and, since this component is essentially dominated by the strength of the composite, there is some potential for improving the initiation energy of the fracture response by increasing the composite strength. An examination of the simple ROM equation;

$$\sigma_c = \sigma_m(1-V_f) + \sigma_f V_f \quad (1)$$

where σ is the strength, V the volume fraction and subscripts c, m and f the composite, matrix and fibre respectively, shows that in the case of a brittle fibre in a ductile matrix (such as in the C/Al system), the composite strength is most affected by the fibre strength and volume fraction. Results from a previous paper [1] indicate that in these C/Al materials the volume fractions were approximately 70% which is close to the maximum packing limit of parallel fibres, consequently the important variable to consider to improve the overall strength of these composites is the fibre strength.

The strength of the as-received fibre can be used in Equation 1 to determine the composite strength. However, such a calculated strength overestimates the true strength of these C/Al composites [1] by a factor of two. It is therefore necessary to consider if the measured composite strengths are a true representation of the composite behaviour or whether the ROM calculation, using the as-received data simply overestimates the composite performance. This paper therefore presents the results of a study into the effect of the preform fabrication route on fibre strength to determine if there is any degradation in the fibre strength at any stage of the process, and therefore if the composite strength and consequently the initiation component of fracture energy can be improved.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

In the present study the fibre used was a PAN-based carbon fibre tow supplied by R.K Carbon Fibres Ltd. The tows consisted of forty thousand filaments and were epoxy-sized. In previous work [1] the fibre tow was filament wound onto a metal spool to produce the initial fibre preform [2], which was given a heat treatment at 350°C for 20 minutes to remove the epoxy size from the surface of the fibres, Table 1. If the desired fracture mode of the composite was brittle, the preform would receive no further heat treatment until the final preheat which consisted of an isothermal hold at 750°C for 10-15 minutes prior to liquid metal infiltration. If a SCP fracture mode was required, the preform would be given a post-desize heat treatment after desizing and prior to the final preheat. The post-desize heat treatment consisted of an isothermal hold at 400°C for three hours followed by a rapid temperature ramp of 10°C/min to 750°C for the final preheat. All the heat treatments were performed in air.

To investigate the effect of the processing route on fibre strength, lengths of fibre tow were subjected to the same heat treatments in air which were used to process the fibre preforms. Tensile tests were performed on the single fibre tows which were embedded in resin after the various heat treatments of the preform processing route, Table 1. Micrographs of the fibre surfaces were obtained by scanning electron microscopy after each heat treatment prior to embedding the fibres in resin. The tow was embedded into the resin by a technique similar to

that reported by Bader et al.[3]. Epoxy/fibre glass laminate end tabs were fixed onto the cured strips to produce a gauge length of 100mm, and the test pieces pulled at a crosshead speed of 5mm/min. The tensile strengths of the individual fibres were determined from the load and total cross-sectional area of the fibres which was calculated from the mass per unit length of the virgin fibre and the fibre density. The latter values were supplied by the manufacturer.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Fibre Strength

The technique of embedding the carbon fibre tows in resin proved successful in producing samples in a suitable form to determine fibre strength values. The as-received fibre strengths appeared quite consistent at approximately 2290 MPa which agrees with the value of fibre strength obtained from the manufacturers. The strengths of the desized fibres however, were approximately 20% less than the as-received fibre, Table 2. The strengths of the fibres which had a post-desize heat treatment could not be determined because the fibres were susceptible to deterioration during heat treatment and became very difficult to embed in the resin as they tended to mat. The fact that this is not observed during the post desize heat treatment of preforms suggests that the thick, tight-knit nature of the preform protects the inner tows from complete degradation. An examination of the composite strengths of infiltrated preforms however, does suggest that the fibre strength is not affected by the post-desize heat treatment, [1]. The final preheat stage resulted in the individual fibre tow rapidly reacting which suggests that severe degradation occurs. In some earlier work [4] on the carbon/aluminium system a desizing temperature of 750-800°C was used on the fibre preforms which resulted in a white ash being present on the surface of the preform. This indicates that even in the case of a preform this temperature regime produces severe attack on the fibre surfaces.

If the desized value of fibre strength (1760 MPa) is used in ROM, Equation 1, it is found that the composite strength values are still greater than those obtained experimentally, Table 3. The ROM equation however, must be modified at high fibre volume fractions to include the situation where some of the fibres are touching and consequently fewer interfaces are available to the matrix during infiltration and there is a reduction in the possibility of load transfer from the fibre to the matrix. This is most certainly the case in this system where the fibre volume fraction is 70%. A model for such behaviour has been proposed by Karam [5] which modifies Equation 1 by the inclusion of an interaction probability ratio which is a function of the ratio of the fibres touching to the total number of interfaces available. This therefore gives;

$$\sigma_c = \sigma_m(1-V_f) + \sigma_f V_f(1-n^2 V_f^2) \quad (2)$$

where n is the fibre interaction probability ratio. The ratio, n, can be obtained directly from optical micrographs of the composites. Table 3 shows that if the Karam modification to ROM is used the values obtained are significantly closer to the experimental values. Since the volume fraction of fibre present has been determined experimentally as has the value of n, the only parameter which can account for the remaining difference is the fibre strength. This therefore suggests that the actual value of the fibre strength is even less than that measured after desizing, possibly due to the final processing of the fibre prior to infiltration.

3.2 Microscopy

Micrographs of the fibre surfaces after each heat treatment stage of the processing route are shown in Figure 2. The surface of the as-received fibre is shown in Figure 2(a), and is similar to micrographs presented by Kim et al.[6] where the surface topography is thought to be due to the oxidative treatment the fibre is subjected to after its manufacture. This treatment is applied to the fibre surface to improve its adhesion to a polymer matrix, and has the effect of altering the surface chemistry of the fibre by increasing the number of oxygen and nitrogen groups on the surface. The surface of the fibre in this condition also contains 1-2% by weight of a proprietary epoxy resin size. The size used by RK Carbon Fibre Ltd. is an uncured water based emulsion of a simple bis-phenol A which is used to bind the fibres lightly together and make the tows easier to handle. Bader et al [3] have indicated that the presence of size on the fibre surface does not affect the tensile strength. To ensure the correct bonding between the carbon fibres and aluminium, the size needs to be removed from the fibre surface which was achieved by heat treating the fibre at 350°C for 20 minutes. Figure 2(b) shows the fibre in this condition and it is obvious that the surface is very similar to that of the as-received fibre. After the post-desize heat treatment however, it is clear that some change in surface topography has occurred, Figure 2(c). This is even more apparent in Figure 2(d) where severe surface attack is evident after the final preheat at 750°C.

4. DISCUSSION

It is clear that the desize heat treatment reduces the strength of the fibre but it is achieved with no apparent change in the fibre surface morphology. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was therefore performed on the fibres to see if it gave any additional information on the heat treatments, Figure 3. The TGA data shows that in the temperature range of room temperature to 350°C, which would be characteristic of a typical isothermal temperature for the desize process, a weight loss of approximately 2% is evident which is consistent with the size content on the fibre. The information does not give any indication of what is happening on the fibre surface during this heat treatment and therefore the nature of this process needs further investigation.

The TGA results show that in the post-desize heat treatment where the fibres are held at 400°C for three hours, there is a small further weight loss of 1-2% which suggests that there is only a limited attack on the fibre surface. Heat treating fibres in air can cause a number of oxidising effects which include the surface pick-up of oxygen and the direct oxidative attack of the fibre. The conditions used in the post-desize heat treatment however, would not be expected to be in the regime of direct oxidative attack although the evidence of surface changes in Figure 2(c) suggest that this may have occurred. There is some evidence to suggest that limited oxidative attack may be possible at temperatures as low as 400°C [7]. There are no gross effects on the fibre however, until approximately 480°C where there is a rapid increase in weight loss due to the direct oxidative attack of the fibre in air. This correlates with Figure 2(d) and the severe attack observed on the fibre surface, which suggests that there would be a further reduction in the fibre strength.

The results so far suggest that the control of the fibre strength is complex and therefore further investigation is required before the process is understood and it can be determined whether the

size can be removed without degrading the fibre strength. The difference between the surfaces of the desized and post-desized fibres only plays a small role in this paper as the present work is concentrating on the aspect of fibre strength. However, although the post-desize heat treatment has no discernible effect on the composite strength, and therefore by implication on the strength of the fibre, it is clear that the subtle changes introduced by the post-desize heat treatment do play a part in introducing SCP. The reason for this is also under investigation.

The study has indicated however, that the composites are obeying ROM if the true fibre strength is considered. Therefore this suggests that any improvement in the initiation component of the fracture energy of composites showing brittle or a SCP fracture mode, must address the effect of the preform heat treatment on the carbon fibre strength.

Acknowledgements

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References

1. Friend, C.M., Winfield, P.H., *The Effect of Fibre Architecture on the Toughness of Unidirectionally Reinforced Metal-Based Composites*, Proceedings of the 6th European Conference on Composite Materials, Bordeaux, 1992, pp 555-561.
2. Kim, J., Lee, S.K., *The Effect of Specimen Size on the Manufacturing Process of Squeeze Cast Metal Matrix Composites*, Composites Design, Manufacture and Application. Proceedings of the 8th International Conference on Composite Materials, Honolulu 1991 (SAMPE 1991) Paper 17K.
3. Bader, M.G., et al., *The Influence of Fibre-Matrix Interface Strength on the Tensile Strength and Failure Mode in Uniaxial CFRP*, *ibid* paper 11-I.
4. P H Winfield - unpublished work.
5. Karam, G.N., *Effect of Fibre Volume on Tensile Properties of Real Unidirectional Fibre-Reinforced Composites*, Composites, Volume 22, No.2, March 1991.
6. Kim, J., et al., *Surface Analysis of Carbon Fibres Modified with PVAL Coating and the Composite Interfaces*, Journal of Materials Science, Volume 27(1992), pp6811-6816.
7. Bansal, R.C, et al., *Active Carbon, Surface Chemical Structures On Active Carbons*. Marcel Dekker Inc.

1.	Desize at 350°C for 20 mins.	DESIZE
2.	Preform put in furnace at 400°C.	POST DESIZE HEAT TREATMENT
3.	Isothermal hold at 400°C for 3 hrs.	
4.	Temperature ramp 400-750°C at 10°/min.	FINAL PREHEAT
5.	Isothermal hold at 750°C for 10mins.	

Table 1. Preform Processing Route

FIBRE SAMPLE	LOAD kN	TENSILE STRENGTH GPa.
As Received	3.78	2.47
	2.15	1.40
	3.55	2.31
	3.43	2.24
	3.99	2.60
	3.17	2.07
	3.60	2.43
	3.75	2.53
	3.90	2.64
	3.31	2.24
Desized	2.97	2.01
	3.29	2.23
	2.47	1.67
	1.69	1.14

Table 2. Tensile Strengths of Epoxy/Carbon Fibre Tows.

Fibre Volume Fraction	Composite Strength Experimental (MPa)	Composite Strength ROM (MPa)	Composite Strength Modified (MPa)
0.76	462	1338	702
0.72	582	1288	732
0.66	878	1187	759
0.73	594	1305	726
0.72	483	1288	732
0.68	740	1221	750
0.74	650	1322	719
0.62	650	1091	765
0.65	500	1171	762
0.76	370	1356	702
0.64	530	1154	756
0.61	540	1103	765
0.67	520	1204	756
0.71	466	1272	739
0.68	361	1221	753
0.75	776	1339	711
0.78	605	1390	683
0.57	483	1036	760

Table 3. Composite Strength Values.

Figure 1 - Typical Load/Displacement Curve for a C/Al Composite Stable Crack Propagation

Figure 2 C-Fibre Surfaces (a) As Received, and Following Exposure to Air at (b) 350°C (c) 400°C (d) 750°C

Figure 3 Weight Loss from an As-received C-Fibre Exposed to Air